

A CONCEPTUAL MODEL FOR A HIGHLY FLEXIBLE GEOSCIENTIFIC LABORATORY DATABASE

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Abstract

A generally applicable database for geoscientific laboratory data is still missing. The variety of both methods and data and the complexity of laboratory studies impede the creation of an appropriate database. With this pilot project, we aimed at the development of a geoscientific laboratory database. We developed a model for a flexible and extensible database applicable to geoscientific laboratory data. This model can work as a basis for the construction of geoscientific laboratory databases. Beside the technical implementation of the database model, the distribution and acceptance of the database model within the relevant communities will be future challenges.

¹ Based on the CRediT Contributor Roles Taxonomy: <https://credit.niso.org/>

I. Introduction

Geoscientific research is an interdisciplinary task, where methods from different disciplines, such as geochemistry, mineralogy, and geophysics, are combined to answer a certain question. For such interdisciplinary studies, the relevant geoscientific data must be provided in a clear and unique way to avoid misinterpretations. However, geoscientific data can be complex and comprises a variety of methods, parameters, and units. The diversity of geoscientific data impedes reuse and interdisciplinary exchange of research data. Bridging the gap between the disciplines and improving the interoperability and reusability of geoscientific data is essential for both the success of interdisciplinary research projects and the sustainability of research data in general. A geoscientific database model applicable to all disciplines would be highly desirable, as it would facilitate a sustainable use of laboriously gathered research data and improve reproducibility of the related scientific results.

However, mapping of geoscientific research data in a common database model is challenging, as the data comprise a variety of formats, types, and sizes. Sometimes, research data are expressed by discipline-specific parameters and in non-systematic units, which impedes the interoperability. Usually, no standards exist for the experimental workflow of geoscientific studies, so that the procedures are individual and therefore difficult to describe consistently. The database model must be extensible in two ways: a) distribution of the database will proceed discipline-by-discipline. Thus, the inclusion of new disciplines in the database model must always be feasible and b) future developments concerning measurement and processing of data will have to be mapped as well in the database. Therefore, extensibility and flexibility are the biggest challenges to a model for a geoscientific laboratory database.

Up to now, few approaches for a laboratory database in geosciences exist. These models are limited to certain disciplines (e.g., Lehnert et al., 2000) and single methods (e.g., SIP-Archiv), respectively. Nevertheless, the existing approaches contain elements that are very useful in the context of a broader geoscientific laboratory database. Concerning the type of database, a relational database model, where data are linked with each other by unique IDs is a widely used model (e.g., Horsburgh et al., 2008; He et al., 2019) as it provides much flexibility. Persistent identifiers, as used by Bär et al. (2020) to assign clearly the origin of samples, help to identify data and to avoid misunderstandings. Describing the experimental workflow by a machine-readable code supports the interoperability of the database model and its accessibility in terms of automatic data collection. The application of thesauri (e.g., Morrill et al., 2021) opens the database to other disciplines as it allows the transfer of discipline-specific parameters. Similarly, a unified code for units of measure (UCUM), as introduced by Schadow et al. (1999), enables a generalization of units.

II. Results

a) Implemented Solution

For our approach, we first distinguished between two phases of a laboratory experiment: the acquisition of data and the interpretation of data, as shown in Figure 1. Some of the metadata relevant in the context of a laboratory experiment, such as information about the measuring device, are the same for every measurement. Accordingly, these metadata only need to be stored once. We labelled this type of metadata as general metadata. Other metadata must be captured for every acquisition and interpretation of data, respectively. Metadata sets containing details on the measurement conditions and on the processing configuration, respectively, are examples for this type that we labelled specific metadata. As shown in the simplified data map in Figure 1, a number of links between the different sets of metadata exist. We mapped these links in our relational database model by using unique IDs to connect different tables of metadata. Figure 1 shows the metadata related with the data from a single measurement that is subsequently processed with a certain algorithm. Real laboratory studies are usually more complex as they often comprise several measurements that may be interpreted with different algorithms. The interpretation of data from an older study with a new algorithm is also a realistic scenario for a laboratory study.

Fig. 1: Simplified data map (Nordsiek and Halisch, 2022b). The flow of data (light green arrows) and the links between different sets of metadata (dark blue arrows) visualize the relationships that exist between metadata of a single laboratory study.

Figure 2 exemplarily demonstrates how the connections between different tables of metadata are organized. Starting with the processing metadata of a data file, a unique ID links these metadata with the according metadata of the measurement. From here, other links with unique IDs provide further information, e.g., on the device used for the measurement and the investigated sample. New devices, samples, and other relevant metadata can be integrated by adding new tables and linking them through unique IDs.

Fig. 2: Example of linked metadata tables (Nordsiek and Halisch, 2022b).

Persistent identifiers are an essential tool to label elements uniquely for everyone and to allow global identification. Persistent identifiers exist not only for documents (DOI), but also for samples (IGSN), researchers (ORCID), and even for research institutions (ROR). We include persistent identifiers in the metadata whenever possible, so that, for instance, samples can be found by their IGSN and researchers by their ORCID, respectively.

A key challenge for a geoscientific laboratory database model is its interdisciplinary usability. We aim to open the database model to different geoscientific disciplines by using discipline-specific thesauri. In this context, the Simple Knowledge Organization System (SKOS) is a suitable data model, where expressions are linked to other expressions through defined relationships. Thus, a hierarchical network of expressions can be organized, extended, and modified without interfering the original database model.

Another issue in terms of the interdisciplinary usability of the database model are possible ambiguities concerning the representation of units in geoscience. The UCUM system (Schadow et al., 1999) allows decomposition of every unit into a superposition of seven base units, comprising the quantities length (in meter), time (seconds), mass (gram), electrical charge (Coulomb), temperature (Kelvin), light intensity (Candela), and angle (radiant). The elements of each 7-dimensional vector describing an arbitrary unit represent the exponents of the according base units. A standardised workflow (Figure 3) has been developed to allow a machine-readable and efficient description of the experimental workflow. Every action related with the measurement is described by a five-word-sentence, with a verb (element 1), subject/object (elements 2 and 4), preposition (element 3) and a term for a duration or frequency (element 5). Thus, even complex sample preparations and measurement procedures, respectively, can be described through a set of standardized expressions.

ID	Element 1	ID	Element 2	ID	Element 3	ID	Element 4	ID	Element 5
0	void	0	void	0	void	0	void	0	void
1	dry	1	sample	1	in	1	sample	1	for 1 h
...	...	2	tank
8	fill	4	with	3	vacuum	4	for 24 h
						8	NaCl solution of 0.1 S/m		

Fig. 3: Standardised workflow with two examples: a) The instruction “dry sample in vacuum for 24 hours” can be expressed by “1.1.1.3.4” and b) the instruction “fill tank with NaCl solution of 0.1 S/m” can be written as “8.2.4.8.0” (Nordsiek and Halisch, 2023).

Four presentations have been created to show the project and its results at national and international meetings. An article for publication in a scientific peer-reviewed journal currently is in preparation:

1. NORDSIEK, S. & HALISCH, M. (2022): NFDI4Earth Pilot Work Package: Improving interoperability and reusability of SIP data. 6th International Meeting on Induced Polarization, Annecy/France, poster presentation, 27 – 30 June 2022.
2. NORDSIEK, S. & HALISCH, M. (2022a): NFDI4Earth Pilot - Ideen, Ansätze, Ziele, Nutzen, Zukunft. LIAG-Seminar 2022, oral presentation, 12 July 2022, online.
3. NORDSIEK, S. & HALISCH, M. (2022b): NFDI4Earth Pilot: Interoperability and Reusability of Geoscientific Lab Data. Mid Term Progress Reports NFDI4Earth Pilots and Incubators, oral presentation, 21 October 2022, online.
4. NORDSIEK, S. & HALISCH, M. (2023): Ein relationales Datenbankkonzept für geowissenschaftliche Labordaten. 83. Jahrestagung der Deutschen Geophysikalischen Gesellschaft, Bremen, oral presentation, 06 – 09 March 2023.
5. NORDSIEK, S. & HALISCH, M. (2023a): Making geoscientific lab data FAIR: A model for a geophysical laboratory database. Article for submission to peer-reviewed journal, in preparation.

b) Data and Software availability

No software or tool based on the database model is available. Conceptual figures and Excel Worksheets are provided via Zenodo.

c) Innovation and FAIRness

We present a database model that is not limited to a certain discipline or method, but is developed to be applicable to a variety of geoscientific laboratory data. By combining different tools that have already demonstrated suitability in the context of database models (e.g., thesauri and a unified system for units), we create a flexible and extensible database model. We considered all aspects of the FAIR data principles from the beginning. However, we put the focus on interoperability and reusability of geoscientific laboratory data, as we think that these two aspects of the FAIR data principles are most critical concerning geoscientific laboratory data.

III. Challenges and Gaps

Compared to the submitted plan for the pilot project, we had to modify the goals of the project. Originally, we planned to develop a web-based interface for different types of geophysical laboratory data and to apply machine-learning algorithms on exemplary datasets. As we faced severe problems concerning the IT infrastructure needed to implement the intended laboratory database, we changed the goals of the project towards the development of a more generalized, i.e. cross-/inter-disciplinary database model. The resulting database model now forms the basis for the implementation of a geoscientific laboratory database that is applicable to different geoscientific disciplines. After implementation of the database model, software tools for automatic evaluation of data, e.g., based on machine-learning algorithms, can be applied to the database.

IV. Relevance for the community and NFDI4Earth

Within the framework of this pilot, we developed a database model for geoscientific laboratory data. In contrast to the originally planned project, an implementation of this model was not feasible. Therefore, the model could not be tested by the geoscientific community and no current impact of the database model can be stated. However, alternative database solutions in the field of geoscientific laboratory data are rare and they are usually limited to certain methods and disciplines, respectively. Consequently, we expect that the developed database model, when implemented, will have a significant impact to the community. As we started the development with a geophysics background, the initial model of the database is intended to work with different geophysical laboratory data. However, due to the diversity of methods usually applied in this field (from simple measurements of a single value to complex μ -CT scans), geophysical laboratory data already comprise a variety of data formats and types. The geophysics community, and especially the groups working with different laboratory methods, will benefit directly from the implementation of our database model. With some adaptations concerning discipline-specific thesauri, the database model will be applicable to neighbouring disciplines as, for instance, mineralogy. Other disciplines within the earth system sciences, e.g., soil physics, may also benefit from the implemented database model after it has been adjusted to the requirements of the respective disciplines. Due to the missing implementation of the database model, the outreach of the pilot project and the resulting database model currently is very limited. Nevertheless, presentations at an international workshop, where the project in general was introduced to potential users of the database model, and at the annual conference of the German Geophysical Society (DGG) have been performed. In the latter case, the final version of the database model has been presented to call attention of the geophysics community to the database model and to the importance of sustainable research data management, in general.

V. Future Directions

The technical implementation of the laboratory database model is the key issue deciding about its future success. When the model has been implemented, the acceptance of the database within the geophysics community must be increased by introducing the laboratory database at meetings of the geoscientific community to potential user groups and by offering workshops, teaching material (e.g., tutorials) and trainings of potential users on how to work with the database. If the geoscientific laboratory database is accepted, it will be a useful tool for geoscientist to discover, access, and reuse data resulting from geoscientific laboratory studies. A geoscientific laboratory database will surely increase the visibility of laboratory studies.

Up to now, a parallel development of different geoscientific databases could be observed, where the solutions were limited to certain fields of application. To make geoscientific data truly FAIR, a general database model is needed, that provides common interfaces for the respective disciplines. Our database model can be opened for other geoscientific disciplines by application of discipline-specific thesauri that will have to be created in cooperation with scientists from the relevant disciplines. Beside such a horizontal extension of the database model, i.e. the inclusion of further disciplines, a vertical extension through incorporation of new methods, devices, and evaluation approaches, for instance, can happen at the same time. Thus, the geoscientific database model can grow in both directions independently. However, a reliable technical infrastructure is essential to gain confidence of the scientific community into the continuity of the geoscientific laboratory database.

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